

Assessment of Fatty Acids and Cholesterol Contents in Five Selected Nigeria Commercial Edible Oil Products

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Abstract-: Edible oils are one of the essential ingredients in food culinary practices worldwide. However, previous research articles have attributed consumption of some edible oil products to various health risk implications. This necessitated the undertaken of this research study to evaluate and assess the fatty acids and cholesterol contents in five selected most commonly consumed Nigeria industrial edible oil products (King' oil, Power oil, Mamador oil, Turkey oil and Local groundnut oil) and their associated health risk implications. HPLC and Liebermann – Burchard methods were used for evaluation of cholesterol contents, while Gas Chromatography – Mass spectrophotometric method was used for evaluation of fatty acid contents in the five selected Nigerian edible oil products. The results generated from the analysis had indicated the level of cholesterol content are relatively lower than the daily recommendation intake standard (20 mg/l) in all the five tested edible oil products. The results also indicated higher percentage level of unsaturated fatty acids contents (range from 73.26 – 84.24%) in all the five tested edible oil products. Moreover, the results indicated higher PUFA/SFA ratio value content above World Health Organization (WHO) permissible standard in King' s oil (1.27), Power oil (2.28) and Local Groundnut oil (1.30) respectively. The results indicated omega-6/omega-3 ratio value content slightly above World Health Organization (WHO) permissible standard (range below) in all the five tested edible oil products. Based on this research analysis, results and observations, it was deduced that the five tested oil products were at free cholesterol health risk implications. But evidence of high health risk implications in respect to percentage level of unsaturated fatty acids contents and moderate health risk implications in respect to omega-6/omega-3 ratio value in all the five tested edible oil products were observed. Moreover, evidence of high health risk implications was also observed in respect to PUFA/SFA ratio value in King' s oil, Power oil and Local Groundnut oil products respectively.

Keywords: edible oil products, cholesterol, fatty acids, health risk implications, health risk safety, PUFA/SFA ratio value, omega-6/omega-3 ratio value.

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1.0 Introduction

Edible oil products are one of the essential ingredients in food culinary practices worldwide (Zelalem *et al.*, 2021). It was approximated that about 75% of the World's commercial edible oil and fat products are derived from plant seeds (oil seeds) products, notably from soybean, cotton, palm, grape and groundnut seeds (Nurhan, 2019; Raven and Johnson, 1999). Edible oil products are important constituents of foods and an essential components of human daily diet (Brahmi *et al.*, 2020). Moreover, the roles and functions of fatty acids from edible oils in biological systems includes; cellular carriers of fat-soluble vitamins (A, D, E, and K), provision of energy, cellular barrier of cell components and lastly cellular processes

of living systems (Stender *et al.*, 2018; Simopoulos, 2016; Lukaszewicz *et al.*, 2004). The roles of cholesterol from edible oils in biological systems are provision of major sterol components in tissues and their biological functions includes; structural compositions, cell membranes fluidity, synthesis of lipid rafts, aids in protein sorting, cellular signalling, and apoptosis (Poian and Castanho, 2015; Ras *et al.*, 2013; Harvey and Ferrier, 2011). For decades, fortification of consumers' dietary food products with required nutrients supplements had improved the health being of both nation and continental populace (Prates and Alfaia, 2002). However, some previously published research articles have attributed some human health risk implications with consumption of substandard and unrefined edible oil products (Feingold, 2021; Micha, *et al.*, 2017; Scaiola, *et al.*

2017; Orsavova, *et al.*, 2015; Tran, *et al.*, 2014; Jacobson, *et al.*, 2012; Atinafu & Bedemo, 2011; Fakheri and Javitt, 2011; Harvey and Ferrier, 2011). Moreover, empirical evidence from Horsu (2015) article had attributed that, 95.6% of edible oil consumers consume unrefined and substandard edible oil products. Therefore, assessment of fatty acids and cholesterol contents in edible oil products and their associated health risk implications is crucial in both nation regulatory and health sectors in their efforts in maintaining health safety of the nation populace. This research study is aimed into collation, evaluation and assessment of fatty acids and cholesterol contents in five selected most commonly consumed Nigerian commercial edible oil products and their associated health risk implications. The objective of this research is to provide health risk implications associated with consumption of each tested commercial edible oil products to both the nation regulatory agencies, health sectors and consumers. This effort would aid the application of necessary measures in maintaining health safety of the nation populace.

2.0 Material and Method

2.1 Collection and Preparation of Samples: Five

(5) most commonly consumed Nigeria commercial edible oil products (King'oil, Power oil, Mamador oil, Turkey oil and Local groundnut oil) were selected and bought from the market. The selected commercial edible oil products are then transferred to Biochemistry Research Laboratory, Department of Biochemistry and Forensic Sciences, Nigeria Police Academy, Wudil, Kano State, where they were sampled into five (5) volumetric flasks labelled as (S1, S2, S3, S4 and S5 respectively) for laboratory test analysis.

2.2 Preparation of Liebermann- Burchard reagent

Liebermann- Burchard reagent was prepared in accordance with Admassie *et al.*, (2021) description, where 7 ml concentrated sulfuric acid and 5 ml glacial acetic acid were added into clean sterile 50 ml test tube. The prepared solution tube was then capped and stored in ice bucket placed in dark cupboard prior to test application.

2.3 Preparation of Standard Cholesterol Solutions and Graph for Liebermann- Burchard Method

Standard cholesterol solutions were prepared in accordance with Admassie *et al.*, (2021) description, where five (5) sterile volumetric flasks labelled as (St-

1, St-2, St-3, St-4 and St-5) were prepared. A volume of 0.5, 1.0, 1.5, and 2.0 ml from standard cholesterol stock solution (2000 mg/L) were pipetted and then added into the four (4) sterile volumetric flasks labelled as (St-1, St-2, St-3 and St-4), while sterile volumetric flask labelled as (St-5) was kept blank (containing no standard cholesterol stock solution). Then, a volume of 2 ml from the prepared Liebermann-Burchard reagent was then added into each of the five (5) volumetric flasks labelled as (St-1, St-2, St-3, St-4 and St-5). The solution in each of the volumetric flasks were then diluted using chloroform (CHCl₃) solution until 7 ml final volume of the volumetric flask was reached. The flasks were then covered with black carbon paper and then kept in the dark cupboard for 15 minutes' period. UV/VIS Spectrophotometer machine was on and set at 640 nm wavelength, then blanked to zero using the solution from volumetric flask labelled as (St-5). The absorbance reading for each of the prepared standard cholesterol solution in the volumetric flasks labelled as (St-1, St-2, St-3 and St-4) were measured using the UV/VIS spectrophotometer and results recorded. Using the absorbance readings and the corresponding prepared standard cholesterol solutions, Liebermann-Burchard standard cholesterol solution graph was plotted.

2.4: Using HPLC Method

The procedure for cholesterol analysis using HPLC method was followed in accordance with Admassie *et al.*, (2021); Almajidi *et al.*, (2015) and Attarde *et al.*, (2010) description, where the oil samples (S1, S2, S3, S4 and S5) are first saponified using 3% ethanolic KOH solution, any non-saponifiable oil sample are solved by slow addition of chloroform until complete solution was formed. HPLC analysis was carried out immediately using Agilent 1100 series. The HPLC was set at C18 column (250*4.0mm, 5 μm), acetonitrile/water (1:1) mobile phase and UV detector set at 239 nm at a flow rate of 0.4 ml/min. Absorbance for each of the five (5) oil samples (S1, S2, S3, S4 and S5) obtained and were recorded. Their corresponding cholesterol concentration was determined using the plotted HPLC standard cholesterol solution graph.

2.5: Fatty acid Estimation Analysis

2.5.1: Using GC-MS method

Fatty acid methyl esters (FAME) solution for each of the five (5) oil samples (S1, S2, S3, S4 and S5) were prepared by Methanolic Borontriflouride (13-15%) following ISO 5509:2000 (E) procedures. The prepared fatty acid methyl esters (FAME) solutions of

the oil samples (S1, S2, S3, S4 and S5) were analysed immediately and the fatty acids compositions for oil samples were determined using gas chromatography (GC) (GC1000 Dani - Italy, 2002) equipped with auto sampler and Flame Ionization Detector (FID) following ISO 15304:2003 (E). The peaks were identified in comparison with the GC-MS data of standard oil fatty acid compositions. The GC-MS data of standard oil fatty acid compositions was then compared with the modern GC-MS library and the fatty acids contents were identified and the results were recorded. The obtained retention time of standard oil run on GC-FID standard with respect to the GC-MS and the percentage composition of FAME prepared from standard oil samples were also determined and the results were recorded. The obtained relative retention times of FAME of sample oil run on GC-FID and GC-MS analysis of Standard oil was compared to determine the compositions of FAME of each oil sample

2.4: Estimation of SFA, MUFA and PUFA percentage.

The percentages of saturated, mono and poly unsaturated fatty acid for each oil sample were calculated using the following formula

$$\text{SFA/MUFA/PUFA} = \frac{\text{Total value of SFA/MUFA/PUFA}}{\text{Sum of SFA/MUFA/PUFA}} \times 100$$

Estimation PUFA: SFA, SFA:MUFA:PUFA, Omega-6/Omega-6 Ratios

The ratio was calculated using the formula

$$\text{PUFA:SFA} = \frac{\text{TOTAL AMOUNT PUFA}}{\text{TOTAL AMOUNT SFA}}$$

Statistical Analysis

Statistical analysis using SPSS software (IBM Corp., USA) version 21.0 was used on the generated mean values from the triplicate data results of the test samples in order to assess and determine the accuracy of the established mean values of the data result as estimated from the test samples (S1, S2, S3, S4 and S5).

4.0 Results and Discussion

4.1: Estimated Cholesterol Content

The data results generated from the estimated cholesterol contents from the five selected and tested edible oil samples (Turkey oil, Mamador oil, King’s oil, Power oil and Local Groundnut oil products) using

the two methods (Liebermann – Burchard and HPLC Methods) were presented in table 1 below.

Table 1. Estimated cholesterol content from the five selected and tested edible oil samples (Turkey oil, Mamador oil, King’s oil, Power oil and Local Groundnut oil products).

Oil Sample	Cholesterol content (mg/l)			
	Liebermann – Burchard Method (mean value)	Liebermann – Burchard Method (Standard deviation)	HPLC Method (mean value)	HPLC Method (Standard deviation)
Turkey oil	0.57	0.00	01.41	0.14
Mamador oil	0.43	0.25	14.74	0.28
King’s oil	5.10	0.35	14.74	0.39
Power oil	2.04	0.12	05.74	0.13
Local Groundnut oil	4.39	0.39	24.31	0.85

The results from the two analysis methods all expressed that cholesterol contents are present in all the five tested edible oil samples (Turkey oil, Mamador oil, King’s oil, Power oil and Local Groundnut oil) though at varying ranges.

Hence, due to the increasing awareness of health risk implications associated with cholesterol content in diets (Zelalem *et al.*, 2021). Qualitative and quantitative measures of cholesterol content in dietary intake are desirable and mandatory. Based on this, comparative analysis of cholesterol content between the five edible oil samples and methodologies. Figure 1 was generated and the result revealed that all the

Figure 1. Line graph showing comparison analysis of cholesterol value compositions between the five edible oil samples (Turkey oil, Mamador oil, King’s oil, Power oil and Local Groundnut oil) and methodologies (Liebermann – Burchard and HPLC Methods).

edible oil sample contained cholesterol in their compositions.

In Liebermann – Burchard Method analysis it indicated that all the five edible oil samples contain cholesterol at varying concentration with Mamador oil containing the least (0.43) followed by Turkey oil (0.57), Power oil (2.04), Local groundnut oil (4.39) and King’s oil containing the highest (5.10). However, in HPLC Method analysis it showed a relative same

but higher results compared to Liebermann – Burchard method. The concentration of the cholesterol content for the five edible oil samples are as follows Turkey oil (1.41), Power oil (05.74), Mamador oil (14.74), Kings oil (14.74) and local groundnut oil (24.31) respectively. According to Kolarič and Šimko, (2020) description, the high values of cholesterol concentration as observed in all the five edible oil samples using HPLC method was as a result of high sensitivity of HPLC method over spectrophotometric method of Liebermann – Burchard method. And the reasons were mainly attributed due to, lower LoD (limit of blank) and LoQ (limit of quantitation) values of HPLC method over Liebermann – Burchard method.

The outcomes of this research finding was supported by the previous work of Okpuzor *et al.*, (2009) and Syed *et al.*, (2003), where the two research authors clearly indicated that cholesterol content is present in vegetative oil products, although in small proportion. Hence, daily recommendation standard for cholesterol intake in human diets varies among health regulatory organizations, societies and communities, but in general, a low concentration of cholesterol in food is often considered to be around 20 mg/l or 0.2 g/100 grams of food. Based on this evidence, comparative analysis of cholesterol content between the five edible oil samples, methodologies and daily cholesterol intake recommendation standard (20 mg/l or 0.2 g/100 grams of food) were made (Figure 1) and the results had clearly indicated although that all the edible oil sample contained cholesterol in their compositions regardless of the two methods used. But the cholesterol contents in all the five edible oil samples were relatively lower than the daily cholesterol intake recommendation standard of 20 mg/l per day.

4.2: Estimated Fatty Acids Contents

The data results generated from the estimated fatty acids contents in all the five selected and tested edible oil products (Turkey oil, Mamador oil, King's oil, Power oil and Local Groundnut oil products) were presented in table 2 below.

Evidence from the above result (table 2) had shown that all the five tested oil samples contain the following fatty acids contents; palmitic acid, oleic acid, linoleic acid erucic acid, myristic acid,

palmitoleic acid, α -Linolenic acid, Arachidic acid, Behenic acid, Lignoceric acid Nervonic acid, Stearic acid and Paullinic acid at a relatively same value concentrations and compositions. But it was observed that palmitic acid, oleic acid, linoleic acid and erucic acid were relatively high in concentration, conversely, myristic acid, palmitoleic acid, α -Linolenic acid, Arachidic acid, Behenic acid, Lignoceric acid and Nervonic acid were relatively in low in concentration in all the tested oil samples respectively. Moreover, it was also observed that Stearic acid and Paullinic acid are relatively moderate in concentration in all the five tested oil samples. Additionally, it was also observed that the composition of saturated and unsaturated fatty between the tested oil sample are relatively the same.

4.3: Evaluation of Total Fatty Acid Ratio

In order to accurately determine the total fatty acid content in all the five tested oil samples, total fatty acid ration was calculated and determined using percentages of saturated fatty acid (SFA), monounsaturated fatty acids (MUFA) and polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFA) as well as the ratio of PUFA/SFA, SFAs/MUFAs/PUFAs, and Omega - 6/ Omega-3 respectively. The data result generated from these evaluations were shown in table 3 below.

4.4: Evaluation of Saturated Fatty Acids

The saturated fatty acid (SFA) as analysed in all the five tested oil samples were Myrsitic acid, Palmitic acid, Stearic acid, Arachidic acid, Behenic acid and Lignoceric Acid respectively. And the data result generated from this research analysis had indicated that the tested oil samples (Turkey oil, Mamador oil, King's oil, Power oil and Local Groundnut oil) contain the following sum of SFA contents: 17.95, 20.97, 18.42 ,15.92, 22.97 and percentage of SFA contents: 20.00%, 26.73%, 22.38%, 15.75%, 22.71% respectively. It was observed that palmitic acid followed by stearic are the most predominant SFA in all of the five tested oil sample (figure 2).

Table 2. Estimated Fatty acids contents in all the five test edible oil samples (Turkey oil, Mamador oil, King’s oil, Power oil and Local Groundnut oil products).

Fatty Acid	Fatty Acid Contents in Oil Samples				
	Turkey oil	Mamador oil	King’ s oil	Power oil	Local Groundnut oil
Myristic C14:0	0.55	0.62	0.59	0.44	0.91
Palmitic C16:0	14.11	16.30	12.18	10.22	13.10
Palmitoleic C16:1 (n-7)	0.33	0.12	0.43	0.15	0.39
Stearic C18:0	2.21	3.12	4.41	3.91	4.69
Oleic C18:1 (n-9)	39.20	41.30	29.14	37.78	34.03
Linoleic C18:2 (n-6)	16.20	3.11	22.45	35.65	29.54
α -Linolenic C18:3(n3)	0.41	0.23	0.91	0.69	0.44
Arachidic C20:0	0.38	0.32	0.36	0.29	0.35
Paullinic C20:1 (n-9/7)	3.11	3.08	4.44	3.39	2.21
Behenic C22:0	0.39	0.32	0.54	0.66	3.36
Erucic C22:1 (n-9)	12.30	9.43	6.36	7.32	11.34
Lignoceric Acid C24:0	0.31	0.29	0.34	0.4	0.56
Nervonic C24:1 (n-9)	0.22	0.19	0.13	0.15	0.24

Table 3. Evaluated total fatty acid ratio in all the five tested oil samples (Turkey oil, Mamador oil, King's oil, Power oil and Local Groundnut oil).

Oil samples	SFA %	MUFA%	PUFA%	UFA (MUFA and PUFA) %	PUFA/SFA	SFAs/MUFAs/P UFAs	Omega-6	Omega-3	Omega-6/Omega-3
Turkey oil	20.00	61.48	18.51	79.99	0.93	1:3:1	16.20	0.41	40:1
Mamador oil	26.73	69.00	4.26	73.26	0.16	7:17:1	3.11	0.23	14:1
King' s oil	22.38	49.22	28.39	77.61	1.27	1:2.2:1.2	22.45	0.91	25:1
Power oil	15.75	48.28	35.96	84.24	2.28	1:3:2.3	35.65	0.69	52:1
Local Groundnut oil	22.71	47.66	29.63	77.29	1.30	1:2.1:1.3	29.54	0.44	67:1

Figure 2. Stacked column graph showing the comparison analysis of total saturated fatty acid (SFA) in and between the five tested oil samples (Turkey oil, Mamador oil, King's oil, Power oil and Local Groundnut oil).

4.5: Evaluation of Unsaturated Fatty Acids (UFA) (MUFA AND PUFA)

The unsaturated fatty acid (UFA) as analysed in all the five tested oil samples were Palmitoleic acid, Oleic acid, Linoleic acid, α -Linolenic acid, Paullinic acid, Erucic acid and Nervonic acid respectively. And the data result generated from this study had revealed that the evaluated total unsaturated fatty acids (UFA) contents in Turkey oil, Mamador oil, King's oil, Power oil and Local Groundnut oil were as 71.77; 57.46; 63.86; 85.13 and 78.19 respectively. While, the evaluated percentage UFA contents in all the tested oil samples (Turkey oil, Mamador oil, King's oil, Power oil and Local Groundnut oil) were 79.99%, 73.26%, 77.61%, 84.24%, 77.29% respectively. Based on this results, it was observed that Power oil sample contains the highest level of unsaturated fatty acid (85.13; 84.24%) while Mamador oil contains the least (57.46; 73.26%) (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Stacked column graph showing the comparison analysis of total unsaturated fatty acid (UFA) in and between the five tested oil samples (Turkey oil, Mamador oil, King's oil, Power oil and Local Groundnut oil).

Evaluation of Fatty Acids Ratio

World Health Organization recommendation standard, indicate that a ratio of 1:1.5:1 for SFAs/MUFAs/PUFAs, (PUFA)/(SFA) at the ratio of 0.8 - 1.0 and a ratio of 5~10:1 for ω -6/ ω -3 PUFAs in dietary oil for consumption should be maintained. Reference to this recommendation, fatty acids ratio in all the five tested oil samples (Turkey oil, Mamador oil, King's oil, Power oil and Local Groundnut oil) were measured and determined. And the generated results from this analysis (table 3) had shown that the PUFA/SFA ratio value in Turkey oil (0.93) was within the World Health Organization (WHO) standard range. The PUFA/SFA ratio in Mamador oil (0.16) was below the World Health Organization (WHO) standard range. The PUFA/SFA ratio value in King's oil (1.27), Power oil (2.28) and Local Groundnut oil (1.30) were all above World Health Organization (WHO) standard range. Moreover, the generated results also indicated that all with the exception of Mamador oil the ratio value of SFAs/MUFAs/PUFAs are relatively within the World Health Organization (WHO) standard range.

Moreover, the generated result from the analysis for omega-6/omega-3 ratio had indicated higher values of omega-6/omega-3 ratio above World Health Organization (WHO) standard range (5~10:1) in all the five tested edible oil samples (table 3). Reference to this finding, it is deduced that all the five tested edible oil samples had omega-6/omega-3 ratio contents higher than the permissible standard range as provided by WHO.

5.0 Conclusion

The research findings from this study analysis had discovered that the cholesterol content in all the five tested edible oil samples were within the World Health Organization (WHO) permissible standard. This indicated that all the five edible oil samples were at health risk safety from cholesterol content (good for human consumption). Moreover, the research study also discovered that all the five edible oil sample tested contain similar levels of saturated fatty acids contents at percentage range compositions of 15.75 - 26.73% and unsaturated fatty acids contents at percentage range compositions of 73.26 - 84.24%. This indicated that all the five tested edible oil products contained high percent composition of unsaturated fatty acids (Palmitoleic acid, Oleic acid, Linoleic acid, α -

Linolenic acid, Paullinic acid, Erucic acid, Nervonic acid) and low percent composition of saturated fatty acids (Myrsitic acid, Palmitic acid, Stearic acid, Arachidic acid, Behenic acid and Lignoceric Acid). Comparison analysis with World Health Organization (WHO) permissible standard indicated that all the five edible oil samples were at health risk safety for human consumption in respect to fatty acids compositions.

However, the research discovered from the fatty acids ratio assessment that Power oil, Local groundnut oil and Kings oil contained relatively higher concentration of PUFA/SFA ratio above the World Health Organization (WHO) standard. This indicated that consumption of such oils samples can lead to the risk of oxidative stress as described by Kang *et.al* (2005). Moreover, the research study also discovered from the assessment of omega-6/omega-3 ratio that all the five edible oil samples contained higher omega-6/omega-3 ratio values above World Health Organization (WHO) standard. This indicated the risk of lipid balance health related implications as described by Fernandez *et. al* (2021).

Conclusively, based on this research study, it is deduced that all the five edible oil samples were at health risk safety for human consumption in respect of cholesterol and fatty acids compositions. Moderately safe for human consumption in respect of Omega-6/Omega-3 ratio composition, lastly, kings oil, power oil and local groundnut oil are not safe for human consumption in respect to their PUFA/SFA ratio composition.

5.1: Recommendations

Based on the results generated from two (2) methods used in cholesterol analysis, this research study hereby recommends the use of HPLC method as the best analytical method in cholesterol analysis from oil products. Moreover, based on the results generated from Omega-6/Omega-3 ratio analysis, the research study recommend evaluation of edible oil products with low Omega-6/Omega-3 ratio values below the standard

Author Contribution

Abubakar, M. A., participated in the designing of the study, statistical analysis of the generated data sets, writing of the paper draft, and manuscript. While, Haruna, S. participated in practical evaluation of the study parameters, generation and gathering of data sets. In overall, all authors approved the final version of the paper manuscript.

Conflict of Interest

No potential evidence of conflict of interest was reported by the authors

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